

GSAEC - Acoustic Echo Cancellation embedded into the Generalized Sidelobe Canceller

W. Herboldt and W. Kellermann*

Telecommunications Laboratory, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg
 Cauerstr. 7, D-91058 Erlangen, Germany
 herboldt@LNT.de, wk@LNT.de

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we examine the integration of acoustic echo cancellation (AEC) with a robust generalized sidelobe canceller (GSC) [2, 3] with regard to exploitable synergies. Since the AEC is located behind the fixed beamformer (FBS) of the GSC only one AEC is required for an arbitrary number of array elements. System analysis shows that ideal suppression of local interferers and of acoustic echoes cannot be achieved simultaneously. However, experiments confirm that the interference reduction (IR) is degraded by less than 3 dB compared to a cascade of AEC and GSC and that the echo reduction is improved by more than 13 dB relative to the GSC in echoic environments.

1 Introduction

Microphone arrays are attractive for rendering the acoustic human-machine interface more comfortable. E.g. for speech interaction with computer terminals, the commonly used headset may be replaced by microphones distributed on the screen chassis. With hands-free acoustic interfaces in cars the handset can be discarded and the quality of single-microphone hands-free systems is surpassed. Especially statistically optimum robust microphone arrays are promising as an effective means to reduce reverberation and to suppress interfering noise sources. However, the widely used GSC [1] is most efficient when only a limited number of directions-of-arrivals (DOAs) and interfering frequencies must be suppressed. Particularly in reverberant environments with several interferers, the interference suppression is reduced significantly. This deficiency motivates the combination of the GSC with acoustic echo cancellation methods. Removing the acoustic echoes by an AEC should allow the GSC to concentrate on local interferers.

Three integration concepts are depicted in Figure 1: AEC followed by GSC (AEC-GSC), GSC followed by AEC (GSC-AEC) and AEC embedded into GSC (GSAEC). The robust GSC is implemented according

to [2] using the adaptation control after [3]. FBS, FBF, ABM, and AIC denote a fixed beamsteerer, a delay-and-sum beamformer, the adaptive blocking matrix, and an adaptive interference canceller, respectively.

Figure 1: GSC with integrated AEC

The attractiveness of the AEC-GSC structure suffers from the large computational load involved: Obviously, the required number of AEC filters is proportional to the number of microphones. As a positive aspect, the individual AECs operate just like in the single-channel case [4]. Another positive synergy effect will be explained in Section 2.

Placing the AEC behind the GSC will reduce the computational load to that of a single AEC filter. However, the AEC will be almost ineffective, since the AEC has to incorporate the strongly time-variant impulse response of the GSC in addition to the impulse response of the acoustic echo path. As the adaptive filter of the AEC is generally much longer than the adaptive filters in the GSC, the AEC adaptation cannot track the GSC coefficients.

Aiming at minimum computational requirements and the necessity to place the AEC module such that the AEC does not feel any repercussions from the adaptive GSC leads to the GSAEC implementation: Here, the AEC module is placed behind the FBF (see Fig. 1).

* This work was supported by a grant from Intel Corp., Hillsboro, OR.

This paper describes and illustrates the convergence behavior and resulting synergy effects of GSAEC in comparison to the AEC-GSC cascade. The characteristics as derived in Section 2 are confirmed by experiments in anechoic and echoic environments as presented in Section 3.

2 PROPERTIES OF GSAEC

2.1 Transient Behavior

The adaptive filters forming the ABM, AIC, and AEC are updated by an NLMS algorithm each [5]. The fact that the filter length of the AEC is generally much longer than the filter lengths of the AIC and the ABM together leads to a significantly higher convergence speed of the GSC relative to the convergence speed of the AEC. Typical numbers range from 200...1000 for AEC vs. 32...128 taps for the GSC for a sampling rate of $T_s = 8$ kHz. Here, a positive synergy can be observed for GSAEC. We assume the presence of both a local interferer and acoustic echoes and we consider the system after initialization or after an abrupt change of the acoustic echo path: Then, the GSC will first attenuate both interferers, thereby providing echo suppression depending on the power ratio relative to the local interferers. With increasing convergence of the AEC more degrees of freedom are available for the reduction of local interferers. In turn, their attenuation will improve until the steady-state will be reached (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Dynamic behavior of GSAEC

2.2 Stationary Characteristics

In contrast to AEC-GSC, the echo remains in the noise-cancelling path of GSAEC (lower path in Figure 1), while it is suppressed in the AEC path. In the following, we investigate to what extent this influences IR and echo-cancellation performance.

First, the optimum Wiener solution of the AIC filters is derived. Then, the GSAEC output signal is calculated and the signal-to-interference-ratio power (SIR) is given.

The analysis is based on the following assumptions:

1. Target signal $t[k]$, loudspeaker signal $n_e[k]$, and local interferer $n_l[k]$ arrive from different DOAs; signal attenuation due to wave propagation will be neglected.
2. The beamsteering module FBS compensates the intersensor propagation delays of the target DOA, which results in a coherent superposition of target-signal components $t[k]$ by the FBF.
3. The AEC removes loudspeaker echoes.
4. The ABM suppresses all target signal components and passes all other portions.
5. Target signal $t[k]$, loudspeaker signal $n_e[k]$, and local interferer $n_l[k]$ are zero-mean stationary processes and are mutually uncorrelated.
6. For the autocorrelation of $n[k] \in \{n_e[k], n_l[k]\}$, we assume

$$E \{n[k - \kappa_i]n[k - \kappa_j - l]\} = \begin{cases} \sigma_n^2 & \text{for } i = j \wedge l = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } (i \neq j \wedge l = 0, \dots, 2L - 1) \\ & \vee (i = j \wedge l = 1, \dots, 2L - 1) \\ \text{arbitrary} & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

with

$$i, j = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$$

$E\{\cdot\}$ expectation operator

L number of filter taps

M number of microphones

σ_n^2 variance of $n[k]$

and κ_i, κ_j denoting the time-delay associated with the i -th and j -th microphone channel together with the intersensor time-delay due to propagation.

This assumption simplifies the optimum filter weight expression and the following discussion considerably. It means that the autocorrelation of the echoes and of the interferer is zero for windows of length of the adaptive filters around the propagation delays. For relevant signals it means that they have to be uncorrelated. However, simulations have shown that the basic results are also valid for correlated signals.

The adaptive AIC filters $\mathbf{w}_i$ and the AIC input vectors $\mathbf{y}_i[k]$

$$\mathbf{w}_i^T = (w_{0,i}, w_{1,i}, \dots, w_{L-1,i}) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_i^T[k] = (y_i[k], y_i[k-1], \dots, y_i[k-L+1]) \quad (2)$$

are combined in two vectors

$$\mathbf{w}^T = (\mathbf{w}_0^T, \mathbf{w}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{M-1}^T) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{y}^T = (\mathbf{y}_0^T, \mathbf{y}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{M-1}^T), \quad (4)$$

respectively (see Figure 1).

Applying assumption 2 through 4 yields

$$y_a[k] \stackrel{2,3}{=} M t[k] + \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} n_l[k - \kappa_{l,j}] \quad (5)$$

$$y_i[k] \stackrel{4}{=} n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i}] + n_e[k - \kappa_{e,i}] \quad (6)$$

$$z[k] = y_a[k] - \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \mathbf{w}_i^T \mathbf{y}_i[k] \quad (7)$$

The Wiener solution $\mathbf{w}_{opt}$ minimizing $E\{z^2[k]\}$ can be written as [5]

$$\mathbf{w}_{opt}^T = E\{\mathbf{y}[k]\mathbf{y}^T[k]\}^{-1} E\{y_a[k]\mathbf{y}^T[k]\}, \quad (8)$$

Using assumption 5 and assumption 6, the i -th component of the second expectation can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & E\{y_a[k]\mathbf{y}_i^T[k]\} \\ & \stackrel{5}{=} E\left\{\sum_{j=0}^{M-1} n_l[k - \kappa_{l,j}]\right. \\ & \quad \left.(n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i}], \dots, n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i} - L + 1])\right\} \\ & \stackrel{6}{=} E\{(n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i}]n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i}], 0, \dots, 0)\} \\ & = (\sigma_{n_l}^2, 0, \dots, 0). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

A similar procedure leads to an expression for the other expectation in Equation 8. That is

$$E\{\mathbf{y}[k]\mathbf{y}^T[k]\}^{-1} = \text{diag}\left((\sigma_{n_l}^2 + \sigma_{n_e}^2)^{-1}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $\text{diag}\{\cdot\}$ denotes a diagonal matrix. The optimum Wiener filters are thus given by

$$\mathbf{w}_{i,opt}^T = \left(\frac{\sigma_{n_l}^2}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2}, 0, \dots, 0\right). \quad (11)$$

Combining Equation 5 through 7 and Equation 11 results in

$$\begin{aligned} z[k] &= M t[k] + \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \left(\frac{\sigma_{n_e}^2}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2} n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i}]\right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\sigma_{n_l}^2}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2} n_e[k - \kappa_{e,i}]\right) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

for the output $z[k]$ of the system.

Obviously, both local interference and echo are weighted by a fraction of the signal energies and remain in the GSC output signal. Echo portions are contained in the input signals of the AIC adaptive filters which are not present in the signal used as reference for the NLMS update. As a result, neither local interferers nor acoustic echoes can be removed completely by this structure.

Now, the SIR of the GSAEC output can be computed from the mean-squares $E\{z^2[k]\}$ based on Equation 12 with the help of assumption 5

$$SIR = \frac{M^2 E\{t^2[k]\}}{A + B} \quad (13)$$

with

$$A = \left(\frac{\sigma_{n_e}^2}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2}\right)^2 E\left\{\left(\sum_{i=0}^{M-1} n_l[k - \kappa_{l,i}]\right)^2\right\} \quad (14)$$

and

$$B = \left(\frac{\sigma_{n_l}^2}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2}\right)^2 E\left\{\left(\sum_{i=0}^{M-1} n_e[k - \kappa_{e,i}]\right)^2\right\}. \quad (15)$$

Three special cases illustrating the upper and lower limits of the SIR are of interest.

First, the acoustic echoes can be ideally suppressed, if the local interferer is zero, and vice versa.

Second, the SIR for the worst case where the acoustic echoes and the local interferer are summed coherently is given by

$$SIR = \frac{\sigma_t^2(\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2)}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 \sigma_{n_l}^2}, \quad (16)$$

with the variance of the target signal σ_t^2 . When the signals $t[k]$, $n_e[k]$ and $n_l[k]$ have identical variances a minimum value of SIR=2 is obtained.

Third, when the acoustic echo and the local interferer are summed incoherently the SIR becomes maximum

$$SIR = \frac{M^2 \sigma_t^2(\sigma_{n_e}^2 + \sigma_{n_l}^2)}{\sigma_{n_e}^2 \sigma_{n_l}^2}. \quad (17)$$

With $\sigma_t^2 = \sigma_{n_e}^2 = \sigma_{n_l}^2$ the SIR simplifies to $2M$ which still represents a 6 dB gain relative to a simple delay-and-sum beamformer.

In practical situations a perfect echo cancellation by AEC will not be attained. Thus, there will always be echo components leaking through the AEC, lessening the leakage of acoustic echoes and of local interferences, and leading to higher SIRs in turn.

3 Evaluation

For verifying the synergy effects the following setup was used. Experiments were performed in both an anechoic chamber and a small corridor of 10m³ with a reverberation time of 750 ms. A linear microphone array consisting of 8 omnidirectional microphones with a spacing of 4cm was placed in parallel to two opposite walls. (Thus, the corridor can be taken as a kind of worst-case scenario in terms of produced reverberation at the array's position.) Low-cost loudspeakers with integrated amplifiers representing the target, the interferer, and the echo source were placed 0, -60, and 90 degrees off-axis, respectively. The distance from the array's phase center to the loudspeakers was 60 cm for the anechoic chamber and 92.5 cm for the corridor. The recorded white noise signals were band-limited to the 500 and 5000 Hz range (sampling rate $f_s = 12$ kHz). The filter lengths of ABM, AIC, and AEC were 16, 20, 1000 (anechoic), and 10000 (echoic), respectively, the associated stepsizes for the NLMS were set to 0.3, 0.01, and 0.1, respectively.

3.1 Transient Behavior

First, the transient behavior was investigated in the anechoic environment. Therefore, the IR evolution after the system's reset was determined. The ABM was initialized with the steady-state filter coefficients and was kept fixed. The AEC and the AIC were updated alternately for 2000 and 70000 iterations, respectively. Thus, a trace for increasing AEC convergence with totally converged AIC is obtained. For the adaptation of the AEC, only acoustic echoes were present, while for the adaptation of the AIC both the local interferer and the far-end signal were active. By using these numbers of iterations the transient behavior of the *echo return loss enhancement* contributed by the AEC $ERLE_{aec}$ and its influence on the reduction of local interferences of the GSC IR is tracked. The results are depicted in Figure 2. It can be seen how the contribution of the GSC $ERLE_{gsc}$ decreases with an increasing echo cancellation of the AEC module $ERLE_{aec}$.

3.2 Stationary Characteristics

Optimum ERLE and IR were also determined after convergence of all adaptive filters. GSAEC was compared with AEC-GSC and GSC without AEC for one- and two-interferers presence in the anechoic and the echoic environment. The adaptation of the different modules was performed sequentially according to the positions in the system. ABM and AEC were adapted with only target-signal or far-end-signal presence, respectively, AIC felt both interfering signals. For ABM, AIC, and AEC 30000, 10^5 , 10^6 (anechoic), 10^7 (echoic) iterations were used, respectively.

Figure 3: Comparison of IR and ERLE in an anechoic (a) and an echoic environment (b)

The results for the anechoic case are shown in Figure

3(a). As one would expect, both $ERLE_{gsc}$ and IR of “GSC single-interferer” are higher than for “GSC two-interferers” because of the limited number of degrees of freedom of the AIC. IR is higher than $ERLE_{gsc}$ due to the dependency of the array pattern on the DOAs. AEC-GSC and GSAEC reflect the increase of degrees of freedom for the reduction of local interference. AEC-GSC almost reaches the IR obtained by “GSC single-interferer”. Consequently, the supplementary ERLE gain by the GSC has to be low. The results for GSAEC correspond to the considerations of the previous section. Both IR and ERLE are less than for AEC-GSC. ERLE is splitted into $ERLE_{aec}$ which is determined between input and output of the AEC and $ERLE_{gsc}$ which is the difference between $ERLE_{gsaec}$ and $ERLE_{aec}$. $ERLE_{gsc}$ takes on a negative value, since acoustic echoes that are cancelled by the AEC, but not suppressed by the AIC, will appear at the system output.

In the echoic environment (see Fig. 3(b)), $ERLE_{gsc}$ and IR_{echo} are deteriorated considerably due to multipath propagation, while $ERLE_{aec}$ is not affected. Here, IR and ERLE can still be improved by using GSAEC, though $ERLE_{gsaec}$ is about 10 dB less than in the anechoic case.

4 Summary

The study of the GSAEC structure has shown that robust echo cancellation performance can be achieved even with a single echo canceller for an arbitrary number of array elements. The interference-reduction quality is almost identical to AEC-GSC, the echo-reduction is improved by over 13 dB relative to a GSC without AEC in echoic environments.

5 Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank David Graumann of Intel for his encouragement and for stimulating discussions.

References

- [1] L. J. Griffiths, C. W. Jim. *An Alternative Approach to Linearly Constrained Adaptive Beamforming*, IEEE Trans. on AP, Vol. AP-30, January 1982.
- [2] O. Hoshuyama, A. Sugiyama. *A Robust Adaptive Microphone Array with Improved Spatial Selectivity and its Evaluation in a Realtime Environment*, ICASSP, Atlanta, April 1997.
- [3] O. Hoshuyama, A. Sugiyama. *A Real-time Robust Adaptive Microphone Array Controlled by an SNR Estimate*, ICASSP, Seattle, May 1998.
- [4] W. Kellermann. *Strategies for Combining Acoustic Echo Cancellation and Adaptive Beamforming Microphone Arrays*, IEEE Proc. ICASSP, Munich, 1997.
- [5] S. Haykin. *Adaptive Filter Theory*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1986.